

1 Structural characterization and extended substrate scope analysis of two 2 Mg²⁺-dependent O-methyltransferases from bacteria

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9 **Two promiscuous O-methyltransferases** from bacteria were found to methylate a panel of catechol
10 substrates towards high-value medicinal compounds. Surprisingly, the non-catechol substrates 5-
11 hydroxyflavonoids and *o*-hydroxybenzoic acids/aldehydes were also methylated at low conversion rates.
12 The crystal structures reveal potential target sites for enzyme engineering for biocatalytic applications.

13

14 Abstract

15 Oxygen-directed methylation is a ubiquitous tailoring reaction in natural product pathways catalysed by
16 O-methyltransferases (OMTs). Promiscuous OMT biocatalysts are thus a valuable asset in the toolkit for
17 sustainable synthesis and optimization of known bioactive scaffolds for drug development. Here, we
18 characterized two bacterial OMTs from *Desulforomonas acetoxidans* and *Streptomyces avermitilis* in
19 terms of their enzymatic properties and substrate scope and determined their crystal structures. Both
20 OMTs methylated a wide range of catechol-like substrates, including flavonoids, coumarins,
21 hydroxybenzoic acids and their respective aldehydes, an anthraquinone and an indole. One enzyme also
22 accepted a steroid. The product range included pharmaceutically relevant compounds such as
23 (iso)fraxidin, (iso)scopoletin, chrysoeriol, alizarin 1-methyl ether and 2-methoxyestradiol. Interestingly,
24 certain non-catechol flavonoids and hydroxybenzoic acids were also methylated. This study expands the
25 knowledge on substrate preference and structural diversity of bacterial catechol OMTs and paves the way
26 for their use in (combinatorial) pathway engineering.

27 **Keywords:** biocatalysis, natural products, methyltransferases

28 Introduction

29 Methylation is a common modification of all major classes of secondary metabolites and alters their
30 physicochemical properties and biological activity. In particular, oxygen-directed methylation (O-
31 methylation) of natural product scaffolds increases their lipophilicity, introduces steric effects that may
32 affect conformation, and stabilizes reactive intermediates in multistep biosynthetic pathways^[1,2].
33 Accordingly, this “methyl effect” is widely used in medicinal chemistry to increase membrane
34 permeability, bioavailability and stability of lead compounds in drug development and modulate their
35 target-binding properties^[2,3].

36 In nature, methylation of hydroxyl groups is carried out by O-methyltransferases (OMTs) – a diverse family
37 of enzymes relying primarily on S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) as methyl donor. One subgroup of
38 secondary metabolite methyltransferases known as Class I or catechol OMTs (COMTs) catalyses
39 methylation of phenols bearing vicinal hydroxyl groups (catechols), often with a preference for one of the
40 two positions^[2]. The resulting mono-O-methylated catechol group, the guaiacol, is a recurring motif in
41 many plant natural products of pharmaceutical and nutraceutical interest, including vanillin, eugenol,
42 capsaicin and methylated flavonoids. COMTs are also well-studied in animals due to their role in the
43 inactivation of catecholamine neurotransmitters and xenobiotics^[4]. One characteristic of COMTs is their
44 dependence on the binding of a divalent cation, usually Mg²⁺, for full catalytic activity. Metal-independent
45 or Class II OMTs, on the other hand, utilize a catalytic base for deprotonation of the target hydroxyl group
46 and have a broader substrate scope than Class I OMTs^[5].

47 While best studied in plants and animals, class I OMTs are also ubiquitous in bacteria. In some cases, they
48 are encoded in secondary metabolite biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs), where they methylate precursors
49 of complex antibiotic agents such as the L-DOPA building block in saframycin MX1^[4] or 4,5-
50 dihydroxyanthranilic acid in tomaymycin^[7]. The guaiacol group is also present in limazepines^[8] and
51 streptonigrin^[9], although the OMTs from the corresponding BGCs have not been characterized. The
52 majority of known bacterial COMTs, however, are encoded outside of BGCs, and their cellular targets and
53 physiological functions remain elusive. Several *in vitro* activity studies demonstrate a high tolerance of
54 bacterial COMTs towards non-natural catechol substrates such as catecholamines, phenylpropanoids and
55 flavonoids^[10–13].

56 Heterologously expressed OMTs have already been successfully integrated in the engineered pathways
57 towards high-value compounds like ferulic acid^[14], curcuminoids^[15] and vanillin^[16–18], with the latter
58 resulting in the establishment of a commercial process. Additionally, a number of recent studies have
59 focused on the fine-tuning of COMT regioselectivity^[12,19], but the substrate scope is mostly confined to
60 plant phenylpropanoids and flavonoids. As O-methylation is one of the most common tailoring reactions
61 in natural product biosynthesis alongside hydroxylation, glycosylation and prenylation, promiscuous
62 OMTs are a valuable asset in the toolkit for pathway engineering and diversity-oriented combinatorial
63 biosynthesis^[20]. To that end, thorough characterization of the substrate and product scope of candidate
64 enzymes is essential to fully exploit their catalytic potential.

65 Here, we report heterologous expression and *in vitro* characterization of two promiscuous O-
66 methyltransferases from bacteria. We evaluated the biosynthetic potential of these OMTs on a set of
67 representative natural product scaffolds, demonstrating the successful methylation of several non-
68 canonical substrates and revealing the substrate-dependent nature of OMT regioselectivity. The product
69 scope of the OMTs included several compounds of pharmaceutical and nutraceutical relevance. We

70 furthermore determined high-resolution X-ray crystal structures of the OMTs to reveal potential target
71 sites for tuning regioselectivity or enhancing the catalytic efficiency by enzyme engineering.

72 Results and Discussion

73 Biochemical characterization and *in vitro* activity assays

74 In a previous study^[14], we used cell-free transcription/translation followed by *in vitro* activity testing to
75 screen a panel of putative O-methyltransferases against several catechol-like compounds. Some of these
76 enzymes catalysed regiospecific methylation of caffeic acid to ferulic acid *in vitro* and in an *Escherichia coli*
77 cell factory. From this set of enzymes, we selected two OMTs for further characterization and substrate
78 scope analysis in this study: the top-performing enzyme StrAOMT from *Streptomyces avermitilis* (UniProt
79 accession: Q82B68), which was previously shown to methylate several flavonoids *in vitro*^[10], and
80 DesAOMT from *Desulfuromonas acetoxidans* (UniProt accession: Q1JXV1) - an otherwise uncharacterized
81 enzyme. DesAOMT struck us as interesting because of its lower molecular weight and the lack of a putative
82 catalytic triad conserved in all known Class I plant and bacterial OMTs^[21]. Both proteins belong to the
83 PF01596 family, characterized members of which include mammalian COMTs, plant caffeoyl-CoA and
84 flavonoid OMTs, and several secondary metabolite OMTs from bacteria and fungi.

85 First, we performed an analysis of the genome neighbourhood^[22] of the OMTs and their sequence
86 homologs to check for clues on the natural substrates and functions of these enzymes (Figure S1). We saw
87 that the StrAOMT gene is surrounded, among others, by domains encoding putative lipase, acetyl-CoA
88 acetyltransferase and cholest-4-en-3-one 26-monooxygenase functionalities, which might be indicative of
89 a steroid metabolic pathway, as well as several transporters and a prenyltransferase-like repeat protein
90 in the extended neighbourhood. This motivated us to include a terpene and a steroid derivative in the
91 substrate scope analysis. In a broader phylogenomic analysis, we noticed that the StrAOMT gene
92 neighbourhood is highly conserved in other *Streptomyces* genomes. The immediate neighbourhood of
93 the DesAOMT gene contains diguanylate cyclase and diguanylate phosphodiesterase domains, which are
94 responsible for the synthesis and degradation of a bacterial messenger cyclic di-GMP (Figure S1). We did
95 not find any literature precedent for an association of such genes with methyltransferases, and this
96 combination of genes does not appear to be conserved among sequence homologues of DesAOMT.

97 Second, we characterized both enzymes biochemically with caffeic acid as a substrate. We cloned the two
98 genes into pET-21b(+) with a C-terminal 6xHis-tag for expression in *E. coli*. We purified the proteins to
99 homogeneity with a two-step protocol comprising nickel-affinity and size-exclusion chromatography (Fig.
100 S2). Next, we confirmed that the purified enzymes were capable of methylating caffeic acid under the
101 previously used reaction conditions^[14,23] to the *meta*- and the *para*-methoxy products, ferulic acid (FA)
102 and iso-ferulic acid (IFA), respectively (Figure 1a). We then set out to investigate their biochemical
103 properties and optimize the reaction conditions. Both enzymes were tolerant to higher reaction
104 temperatures with the maximum catalytic activity at 40°C and 45°C for DesAOMT and StrAOMT,
105 respectively (Figure 2b). We confirmed that both enzymes are dependent on Mg²⁺ for catalytic activity
106 (Figure 2c, d): the addition of Ca²⁺ or ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) fully inhibited both enzymes,
107 whereas we observed weak residual activity in reactions with no additives ("none"). This may be
108 attributed to the presence of residual Mg²⁺ from protein purification and storage. Alkaline conditions were
109 preferred by both enzymes with an optimum at pH 8–8.5 in Tris-HCl buffer (Figure 1e, f). It is noteworthy
110 that increasing the pH prompted a noticeable shift in regioselectivity of StrAOMT, while overall
111 maintaining a preference for the *meta*-isomer (ferulic acid). With a drop in overall activity, StrAOMT

112 appears to become less regioselective at pH higher than 8.0. DesAOMT showed overall lower
 113 regioselectivity that remained stable across a wide pH range. Overall, with the optimized temperature
 114 and buffer conditions (37°C, Tris-HCl pH 8) and by using a 5-fold excess of SAM, we achieved ~85%
 115 conversion of caffeic acid by both enzymes in one hour. Higher conversion rates could be achieved by
 116 further increasing the concentration of SAM.

117 Since several compounds in our intended substrate panel are poorly soluble in water, we sought to
 118 explore how tolerant DesAOMT and StrAOMT are to organic solvents. To our surprise, increasing
 119 concentrations of dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and acetonitrile (ACN) to 20% (v/v) virtually did not affect

120
 121 Figure 1. Biochemical properties of DesAOMT and StrAOMT with caffeic acid as substrate. Standard reaction conditions (if not
 122 stated otherwise): 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 20 mM MgCl₂, 100 μM caffeic acid, 200 μM SAM, 1 μM enzyme; 1 h at 37°C without
 123 shaking. a) Chromatogram of the OMT-catalysed reactions compared to the no enzyme control (“ne”) (λ=310nm); b) substrate
 124 conversions at different reaction temperatures; c-d) substrate conversions with added Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, EDTA, or no additives (“none”);
 125 e-f) substrate conversions at different buffer pH (buffers: NaPi pH 6; HEPES pH 7; Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 8, 8.5; Glycyl-NaOH pH 9, 10, 11);
 126 g-h) substrate conversions in the presence of organic solvents; i-j) Michaelis-Menten kinetics of StrAOMT and DesAOMT. The data
 127 are represented as mean ± standard deviation of three technical replicates. The full statistical report non-linear regression is
 128 shown in Table S1.

129 catalytic activity of the OMTs, while methanol inhibited DesAOMT only at the highest concentration
130 (Figure 1g, h).

131 Lastly, we determined the apparent Michaelis-Menten kinetic parameters at a fixed SAM concentration
132 of 1 mM at 37°C and pH 7.5. We stopped the reactions after 5, 10, and 15 min and determined the product
133 concentrations by HPLC to estimate the initial reaction velocities using linear regression (Figure S3).
134 Overall, DesAOMT had a lower apparent K_m for caffeic acid than StrAOMT, while k_{cat}/K_m values were similar
135 for the two enzymes (Figure 1i, j). During this series of experiments, we also noticed strong enzyme
136 inhibition at higher substrate concentrations for both enzymes (8000-fold molar excess of substrate over
137 enzyme). A similar observation was previously reported for the bacterial OMT SafC with caffeic acid and
138 dopamine as substrates^[6], but the mechanism of this inhibition is not fully understood.

139 **DesAOMT and StrAOMT methylate a variety of catechol-like scaffolds with differing**
140 **regioselectivity**

141 Next, we set out to assess the performance of DesAOMT and StrAOMT on a range of catechol-like
142 substrates representative of natural product scaffolds, including flavonoids, coumarins, benzoic and
143 resorcylic acids and their respective aldehydes, an anthraquinone, an indole, a terpene and a steroid
144 (Figure 2a, Figure S4).

145
146 **Figure 2. *In vitro* activity and regioselectivity of DesAOMT and StrAOMT with catechol-like**
147 **substrates highlighting possible O-methylation sites in red and blue; b) HPLC-based identification of reaction products of StrAOMT**
148 **and DesAOMT exemplified by substrate 6. Solid lines – reaction products, dashed lines – authentic standards of the potential**
149 **products isofraxidin (triangle) and fraxidin (diamond), ne – “no enzyme” control; detection at $\lambda = 310$ nm; c) and d) conversion of**
150 **substrates 1-10 into the two possible products depicted as stacked histograms (colour coding according to panel a).**

151 We incubated 0.5 mM of the respective substrate with 5 μ M DesAOMT or StrAOMT for 16 h at 37°C. We
152 performed the assays at pH 7.5 in view of instability of some substrates in alkaline conditions and added
153 10-20% DMSO for better solubility of substrates and their methylated products.

154 Both OMTs exhibited remarkable tolerance towards diverse catechol-like substrates with high conversion
155 rates for substrates **1-10** (Figure 2c, d) and moderate to low conversion rates for substrates **17-24** (Figure
156 S4). For the latter substrates, we detected putative methylated products by LC-MS, however, we did not
157 characterize the products any further because the reference compounds were unavailable and the low
158 turnover yields did not warrant in depth structural characterization. Nevertheless, the low level of
159 enzymatic activity observed for these substrates might be an interesting starting point for further
160 investigation.

161 For substrates **1-10** we confirmed the identity of the products by comparing the HPLC retention times and
162 mass over charge values to those of authentic standards (Figure S5) and thereby assessed the
163 regioselectivity of the enzymes. We found that it depends on the chemical scaffold and differs between
164 the two enzymes. Both were selective for the *meta* hydroxyl of phenolic acids and aldehydes **1-3** and
165 aesculetin **4**, but exhibited notable differences when challenged with bulky or highly asymmetric
166 substrates, most notably the coumarins **5** and **6**. StrAOMT was selective for the 8-OH of **5** but methylated
167 its 6-methoxy derivative **6** to a mixture of products with only slight preference for the 7-OH to form
168 fraxidin. On the contrary, DesAOMT was selective for the 7-OH of **5** but produced mostly the 8-O-
169 methylated isofraxidin when challenged with **6** (Figure 2b). Curiously, we observed exclusive conversion
170 of **7** to 3-O-methylated chrysoeriol by both enzymes, which may be attributed to the rigidity and
171 asymmetry of the molecule. Lastly, StrAOMT also converted the steroid **10** to a mixture of 2- and 3-
172 methoxy products. This is consistent with our analysis of the gene neighbourhood of the StrAOMT
173 encoding gene and may indicate that the enzyme has a natural function in steroid metabolism. Overall,
174 our substrate scope analysis with catechol substrates demonstrates the substrate-dependent nature of
175 COMT regioselectivity *in vitro* and highlights the importance of such studies.

176 [DesAOMT and StrAOMT also accept non-catechol substrates](#)

177 After we characterized the substrate scope of both enzymes for the typical catechol-like substrates, we
178 turned to non-canonical phenolic substrates (Figure S4, **26-31**). As expected, many compounds were not
179 methylated, such as those with a single (*m*-coumaric acid) or several *meta*- or *para*-positioned hydroxyl
180 groups (resorcinol, hydroquinone), and phenols with other vicinal substitutions (4-chloro-3-
181 hydroxybenzoic acid, 3-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid). This is probably due to their inability to adopt the
182 proper orientation in the active site and/or coordinate the Mg²⁺ effectively. Similarly, isoferulic acid was
183 not further converted into the dimethylated product.

184 Unexpectedly, our LC-MS results suggest that StrAOMT and DesAOMT also accept non-catechol flavonoids
185 **11-13** (chrysin, pinocembrin and naringenin), albeit with low (<10%) conversion rates. Additionally,
186 StrAOMT can methylate **14-16** (*p*-orsellinic acid, orcinolaldehyde and 2,6-dihydroxybenzoic acid) with low
187 conversion rates (Figure 3a).

188

189 Figure 3. Non-catechol substrates accepted by StrAOMT (**11-16**) and DesAOMT (**11-13**). a) Panel of non-catechol substrates
 190 highlighting putative O-methylation sites in blue; b) and c) elution profiles of StrAOMT-catalysed reactions of **11** and **14** compared
 191 to “ne” control and reference compounds of the opposite regioisomers (dashed line); inserts: mass spectra of the putative
 192 product peaks (triangle). Detection was performed at $\lambda = 310$ nm. Dimethylated products were not observed.

193 The methylated products of flavonoids **11-13** eluted earlier than their substrates (Figure 3b and S6), which
 194 is atypical since methylation generally increases hydrophobicity of a given compound. Such an elution
 195 profile is consistent with literature reports of 5-O-methylated flavonoids^[24], suggesting that **11-13** are
 196 methylated to chrysin-5-methylether, alpinetin and naringenin-5-methylether, respectively. This
 197 assumption is further supported by the fact that the techtochrysin standard – the only other possible
 198 methylation product of **11** – does not coelute with the reaction product peak (Figure 3b). Similarly, the
 199 product of **14** does not coelute with the readily available authentic standard of the corresponding methyl
 200 ester (Figure 3c), which suggests that **14** is methylated at either of the two phenolic hydroxyl groups.
 201 Based on the inability of DesAOMT and StrAOMT to accept **25-27**, it is plausible that **15** and **16** are also
 202 methylated at the *o*-hydroxyl position.

203 Thus far, methylation of *o*-hydroxybenzoic acids in natural products has only been described for metal-
 204 independent enzymes following a different mechanism, as exemplified by calicheamicin orsellinate 2-O-
 205 methyltransferase^[25]. The biosynthesis of 5-methoxyflavonoids remains elusive. Therefore, our findings
 206 for these two bacterial COMTs are rather unusual. Mechanistically, however, it is possible that some non-
 207 catechol substrates can chelate Mg^{2+} and thus serve as substrates for COMTs, as exemplified by the potent
 208 human COMT inhibitors hydroxyquinoline and tropolone^[4]. In addition, the observed 5-O-methylation of
 209 flavonoids may be attributed to enolization of the C-4 carbonyl in a conjugated flav(an)one system, with
 210 the resulting hydroxyl group participating in Mg^{2+} coordination.

211 In order to elucidate the basis of the differing substrate scope and regioselectivities of DesAOMT and
 212 StrAOMT, we next turned to the structural characterization of these enzymes.

213 Crystal structures of StrAOMT and DesAOMT

214 We determined the crystal structures of apo-DesAOMT at 1.5 Å, apo-StrAOMT at 1.5 Å and SAH-bound
 215 StrAOMT at 1.8 Å resolution (Table S2). One asymmetric unit (ASU) of the ligand-free StrAOMT contains

216 two copies of the dimer forming an interface in the substrate-binding site, while a canonical COMT dimer
 217 is present in the ASU of the SAH-bound structure (Figure 4a). The crystals of the latter were obtained
 218 through co-crystallization of StrAOMT with SAM, Mg²⁺ and caffeic acid, suggesting that the enzymatic
 219 reaction proceeded *in situ* and the co-product, SAH, remained bound in the active site. Each StrAOMT
 220 monomer in both structures adopts the Rossmann fold characteristic of SAM-binding proteins, with seven
 221 core β -strands surrounded by eight α -helices. The conformation of the apo- and the ligand-bound form of
 222 StrAOMT is highly similar, with an average C α RMSD of 0.451 between the monomers. Most notably, SAH
 223 binding induces conformational changes in the loop region between $\alpha 2$ and $\alpha 3$ adjacent to SAH (Figure
 224 4b). A search^[26] for structural homologs of the ligand-free structure of StrAOMT identified *Bacillus cereus*
 225 BcOMT2 as the top hit (PDB: 3DUW, Z-score 36.6, RMSD 1Å), closely followed by NkCOMT from *Niastella*
 226 *koreensis* (PDB: 7CVX), TomG from *Streptomyces regensis* (PDB: 5N5D), a putative OMT from *Klebsiella*
 227 *pneumoniae* (PDB: 3TWF) and Rv0187 from *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (PDB: 6JCL) (Table S3). The
 228 largest conformational diversity between these structures is observed in the so-called insertion loop
 229 between $\beta 5$ and $\alpha 8$ (Figure 4d) – a region implicated in binding Coenzyme A and substrate specificity in
 230 plant COMTs.

231 The ASU of DesAOMT contains a single monomer (Figure 4c), but the canonical dimer interface can be
 232 identified between two adjacent ASUs. Furthermore, we believe that DesAOMT forms a dimer in solution
 233 based on its elution profile during size exclusion chromatography (Figure S2). The otherwise canonical

234
 235 Figure 4. Crystal structures of StrAOMT and DesAOMT. Cartoon representation of a) SAH-bound StrAOMT dimer (holo-, PDB:
 236 8C9S); b) superimposed structures of apo- (grey, PDB: 8C9T) and holo-StrAOMT (purple) zoomed in on the $\alpha 2$ - $\alpha 3$ loop adjacent to
 237 the ligands ; c) apo-DesAOMT monomer (PDB: 8C9V); d) comparison of the insertion loops ($\beta 5$ - $\alpha 8$) across DesAOMT (green),
 238 StrAOMT (purple), LiOMT (yellow, PDB: 2HNK), SafC (pink, PDB: 5LOG) and rat COMT (grey, PDB: 1H1D); e) superimposed
 239 monomer structures of holo-StrAOMT (purple) and DesAOMT (green).

240 Rossman fold of DesAOMT is devoid of the N-terminal α -helix, which is present in all known COMT
241 structures determined to date and has been implicated in catalytic activity^[27] and dimerization^[28]. In
242 general, DesAOMT shares little structural similarity with characterized OMTs, the top hit being LiOMT
243 from *Leptospira interrogans* (PDB: 2HNK, Z-score 26.1, RMSD 1.8 Å), followed by putative OMTs from
244 *Coxiella burnetii* (PDB: 3TR6, Z-score 25.2, RMSD 1.8 Å) and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (PDB: 5X7F, Z-
245 score 25.1, RMSD 2 Å), SafC from *Myxococcus xanthus* (PDB: 5LOG, Z-score 25.1, RMSD 1.9 Å) and Rv0187,
246 which is also a structural homolog of StrAOMT. Apart from the missing N-terminal helix, a distinct
247 structural feature of DesAOMT is a short insertion loop typical of animal rather than bacterial COMTs
248 (Figure 4d). When comparing with the StrAOMT structures, the RMSD of C α is even higher (2.2 Å) and
249 several conformational differences are apparent (Figure 4e). The most noticeable ones are in the insertion
250 loop and the β 6- β 7 loop regions.

251 Active site architecture of StrAOMT and DesAOMT

252 Both DesAOMT and StrAOMT possess a metal-binding site conserved across all COMTs: D129, D155, N156
253 in the former and D141, D167, N168 in the latter (Figure S9). In the DesAOMT and holo-StrAOMT
254 structures, we observed electron density in the expected position between these conserved residues and
255 interpreted it as Mg²⁺. An interpretation as Ca²⁺ would also be possible for the DesAOMT structure, since
256 this enzyme was crystallized in a buffer with a mix of divalent metal ions. There might in fact be a mix of
257 ions occupying the binding sites throughout the crystal of DesAOMT. In the holo-StrAOMT structure, we
258 observed additional electron density that we interpreted as 2-pyrrolidone that likely originated from the
259 crystallization solution. The position of this electron density is not near the catalytic residues and is
260 unlikely to be representative of a substrate- or product-bound state.

261 Despite numerous attempts, co-crystallization and soaking of StrAOMT with caffeic acid or aesculetin
262 failed to yield substrate-bound crystals. Therefore, we compared the holo-StrAOMT structure to that of
263 its structural homolog NkCOMT, which is complexed with the substrate protocatechuic acid (PDB: 7CVX,
264 chain A) (Figure 5a). The positions of Mg²⁺ and SAH are almost identical in holo-StrAOMT and NkCOMT, as
265 are the residues lining the active sites of the two enzymes. Apart from the Mg²⁺ ion, catalytic activity of
266 known catechol OMTs seems to rely on the absolutely conserved active site triad K-N-D, which is thought
267 to facilitate deprotonation of the aromatic substrate prior to methyl transfer^[21]. K144, N168, and D215 of
268 StrAOMT are aligned with K142, N166, and D213 of NkCOMT, respectively, forming a typical catalytic triad
269 in the active site. Additionally, K212 of StrAOMT is aligned with K210 of NkCOMT, which closely
270 approaches the 4-hydroxyl group of the substrate. This double-lysine arrangement is shared by other
271 structural homologs of StrAOMT (PDB: 3DUW, 6JCL and 3CBG) (Figure S9). The importance of this
272 conservation is stressed by the fact that the 4-hydroxyl binding lysine of 3CBG, which was also shown to
273 be essential for catalytic activity^[27], is residue three of the amino acid chain and is brought into the active
274 site by the N-terminal loop. The aromatic ring of dihydroxybenzoic acid in NkCOMT is sandwiched
275 between I39 and R169, which are aligned with I41 and R171 in StrAOMT.

276

277 Figure 5. Active site architectures and substrate-binding pockets of DesAOMT and StrAOMT. a) Superimposed structures of holo-
 278 StrAOMT (purple) and NkCOMT (grey) complexed with protocatechuic acid (PCA) (PDB: 7CVX); b) superimposed structures of
 279 DesAOMT (green) and SafC (grey) complexed with dopamine (LDP) (PDB: 5LOG).

280 The closest substrate-bound structural homolog of DesAOMT is SafC complexed with dopamine (PDB:
 281 5LOG). It must be noted that the unresolved portion of the loop between $\alpha 2$ and $\alpha 3$ imposes limitations
 282 on the examination of the active site of DesAOMT; however, several distinct structural features are
 283 apparent. As predicted, R132 of DesAOMT is aligned with K145 of SafC, which was shown to be essential
 284 for its catalytic activity, while the remaining putative catalytic residues N169 and D212 are aligned with
 285 N156 and K186 in DesAOMT. The latter is located within 5 Å of the putative substrate position and might
 286 interact with its other hydroxyl group provided that SAM-induced conformational changes bring it closer
 287 to Mg^{2+} (as observed for SAH-bound StrAOMT). DesAOMT is thus the first characterized COMT bearing an
 288 arginine in place of the absolutely conserved active site lysine. In the enzyme similarity network generated
 289 by Haslinger et al. (Figure S7), the subcluster harbouring DesAOMT (mostly featuring sequences from
 290 extremophile bacteria) shares its characteristic features: the active site R-N-K triad, a short insertion loop
 291 and a missing N-terminal α -helix (Figure S8). Taken together, these observations might be hinting at a
 292 new, possibly more ancient, subgroup of bacterial COMTs.

293 While in plant COMTs the conserved catalytic triad K-N-D was deemed essential for catalysis^[21], there is
294 no clear consensus on the involvement of the catalytic residues in bacterial COMTs. It is generally assumed
295 that the conserved lysine facilitates deprotonation of a hydroxyl group of the substrate, but results of
296 mutagenesis studies are often inconsistent, ranging from a complete loss of activity^[23] to its slight
297 reduction with a change in the regioselectivity profile^[11]. In SynOMT, on the other hand, mutating K3,
298 which is not part of the assumed catalytic triad and is structurally conserved only in a subgroup of bacterial
299 COMTs, completely abolished activity. The unique active site architecture of DesAOMT adds to the long-
300 standing ambiguity surrounding the reaction mechanism of bacterial COMTs, calling for dedicated
301 mechanistic studies like the ones conducted for plant COMTs.

302 Structural determinants of substrate specificity and regioselectivity

303 In model COMT structures, the catalytic Mg²⁺ is located at the bottom of a deep groove lined
304 predominantly with hydrophobic residues, which a catechol substrate can penetrate in two possible
305 orientations. Catechols with polar or ionizable side chains are more likely to orient towards the solvent,
306 while substrates with more hydrophobic substituents may favour orientation towards the “hydrophobic
307 wall” of the enzyme; this results in *meta*- or *para*-selective methylation, respectively^[29]. Thus, the
308 regioselectivity of COMT-catalysed methylation is largely dictated by the chemical nature of the substrate,
309 which is also apparent from the regioselectivity patterns of DesAOMT and StrAOMT. For instance, **6** differs
310 from **5** only by an 8-methoxy group, yet StrAOMT exhibits opposite regioselectivities with these two
311 substrates.

312 Accordingly, engineering efforts to modulate the regioselectivity of COMTs have focused mainly on
313 mutating the residues lining the catechol-binding pocket. A notable example is the Y51R mutation in
314 PFOMT, which alone led to the production of a 1:1 mixture of methylated eriodyctiol products (as opposed
315 to the exclusive *meta* methylation of the wild-type enzyme), while complete transition to *para* selectivity
316 was achieved by an additional N202W mutation at the opposite site of the catechol pocket^[19]. In that light,
317 some of the promising candidates for site-directed mutagenesis include R171, I41 and D215 in StrAOMT
318 or H160, A18 and K186 in DesAOMT.

319 Interestingly, despite having highly similar active site architectures, NkCOMT and StrAOMT exhibit
320 differences in the methylation of protocatechuic acid under similar reaction conditions. While the former
321 produced an equal mixture of *meta* and *para* methylated products^[30], StrAOMT was clearly selective
322 towards the *meta* isomer vanillic acid. This suggests that structural elements distant from the active site
323 may as well influence the regioselectivity of methylation. One such element might be the variable loop
324 connecting the β 5 strand with the α 8 helix. Originally spotted as the main difference between animal and
325 plant COMTs, this “insertion loop” is believed to provide a scaffold for the binding of caffeoyl-CoA in
326 specialized plant enzymes^[31]. A somewhat extended and highly variable loop is also found in the structures
327 of all bacterial COMTs, including StrAOMT. However, its implications in the substrate specificity of
328 bacterial enzymes remain unclear and probably do not involve the binding of CoA^[6]. Curiously, DesAOMT
329 is the first characterized bacterial COMT that possesses a short, animal COMT-like β 5- α 8 loop. Overall,
330 regioselectivity of DesAOMT and StrAOMT appears to be dictated by a complex interplay between the
331 chemical nature of the substrate, structural elements of the enzyme and reaction conditions, which
332 agrees with reports for other COMTs^[12,14,23]. The structures of StrAOMT and DesAOMT may be used for
333 deeper investigation of the COMT reaction mechanism and protein engineering efforts to modulate
334 regioselectivity or affinity towards selected substrates. The latter possibility is particularly intriguing with

335 5-hydroxyflavonoids and 2-hydroxybenzoic acids, which were discovered to be accepted by two bacterial
336 catechol OMTs in this study.

337 Conclusion

338 We performed thorough *in vitro* characterization of two promiscuous Class I O-methyltransferases from
339 bacteria and determined their substrate and product scope, methylation regioselectivity and crystal
340 structures. Both enzymes operated in a broad temperature and pH range, exhibited tolerance to organic
341 solvents and methylated a broad range of natural product scaffolds with differing regioselectivities, which
342 makes them excellent candidates for pathway engineering and combinatorial biosynthesis applications.

343 Our findings suggest that with optimized reaction conditions or further enzyme and pathway engineering,
344 DesAOMT and StrAOMT could provide a sustainable alternative for the production of several natural
345 products of demonstrated pharmaceutical relevance, such as (iso)fraxidin, iso(scopoletin), chrysoeriol,
346 alizarin 1-methyl ether and 2-methoxyestradiol. All of these compounds are currently sourced either from
347 producer plants or through chemical synthesis.

348 We found that StrAOMT and, to some extent, DesAOMT can methylate *o*-hydroxybenzoic acids and 5-OH
349 flavonoids, which have not been associated with this class of enzymes before. To the best of our
350 knowledge, this is the first report of the enzymatic synthesis of the 5-O-methyl ethers of naringenin,
351 chrysin and pinocembrin. The latter, better known as alpinetin, is a rare flavonoid with demonstrated
352 potential for the treatment of acute colitis^[32], among other conditions. As the native biosynthetic pathway
353 for alpinetin remains unknown, and no flavonoid-5-OMTs have been described in the literature, StrAOMT
354 is a good candidate for directed evolution efforts towards the improved enzymatic production of this and
355 other 5-O-methylated flavonoids. The structural insights generated in this study may facilitate rational
356 engineering of StrAOMT and DesAOMT towards the improved turnover of non-natural COMT substrates
357 to valuable pharmaceuticals. Last but not least, the findings from our substrate scope analysis may provide
358 inspiration for the development of new human COMT inhibitors.

359 Experimental section

360 Expression, purification and storage of DesAOMT and StrAOMT

361 The genes encoding DesAOMT and StrAOMT were subcloned into pET-21b(+) with a C-terminal 6xHis-tag.
362 Plasmids harbouring the OMT genes were transformed into chemically competent *E. coli* BL21(DE3) and
363 maintained on selective LB agar containing 100 mg/mL ampicillin. A starter culture was inoculated from a
364 single colony (5 mL, LB with ampicillin) and incubated at 37°C (180 rpm, overnight). The main culture was
365 inoculated from the starter culture (1:100) into auto-induction medium (2% w/v tryptone, 0.5% w/v yeast,
366 0.5% w/v sodium chloride, 25 mM disodium hydrogen phosphate dihydrate, 25 mM potassium
367 dihydrogen phosphate, 0.6% v/v glycerol, 0.05% w/v glucose, 0.0128% w/v lactose) and incubated at 37°C
368 (180 rpm, 2h), after which the temperature was lowered to 18°C (180 rpm, overnight). All following steps
369 were performed with chilled buffers. The cells were harvested by centrifugation (15 min, 3428 x g) and
370 the pellet was resuspended in 5 volumes of the lysis buffer (buffer A including one EDTA-free protease
371 inhibitor tablet (Roche); buffer A: 50 mM Tris/HCl pH 7.5, 500 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole). The cell
372 suspension was lysed by sonication (40% duty cycle, 6 cycles of 30 s ON/30 s OFF) and cleared by
373 centrifugation for 60 min at 25000 x g. The supernatant was loaded onto a HisTrap HP Ni-NTA column (GE
374 Healthcare, USA) connected to an ÄKTA Pure system (Amersham Bioscience, Uppsala, Sweden) and eluted

375 with a linear gradient 0-100% of buffer B (50 mM Tris/HCl pH 7.5, 500 mM NaCl, 500 mM imidazole).
376 Elution fractions corresponding to the protein peak were analysed by SDS PAGE. Fractions with low
377 protein background were pooled and subjected to size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex 75 pg
378 column (GE Healthcare, USA) in the storage buffer (DesAOMT: 10 mM Tris/HCl pH 7.4, 20 mM NaCl, 0.2
379 mM MgCl₂, 5 mM BME; StrAOMT: 10 mM HEPES pH 7, 200 mM NaCl, 0.2 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM DTT, 5% v/v
380 glycerol). The protein concentration was determined by absorbance at 280 nm (NanoDrop, ThermoFisher
381 Scientific, USA) before the purified enzymes were aliquoted and flash-frozen with liquid nitrogen for
382 storage at -80°C.

383 Differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF)

384 For each screening, 0.5 mL of a 1–2 mg/mL protein sample was mixed with 2.5 µL of SYPRO® orange dye
385 (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA) and aliquoted at 5 µL before being mixed with 45 µL of the respective
386 screening buffer. Thermal stability of the protein samples was measured in a CFX96 Dx Real-Time qPCR
387 instrument (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA); program: 20°C for 2 min, 20–95°C over 117 min. Protein melting
388 temperatures (T_m) under the different buffer conditions were determined from the maximum value of
389 the first derivative of the melting curve.

390 Activity tests

391 The initial conditions for the *in vitro* OMT reaction were adapted from Siegrist et al.^[23] and included 50
392 mM HEPES/NaOH pH 7, 20 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM SAM, 0.5 mM substrate (from 80 mM stock in DMSO) and
393 5 µM enzyme in a total volume of 42 µL. The reactions were started by the addition of the enzyme (or
394 water for the "no OMT" control). The reactions were incubated for 1h at 30°C unless stated otherwise,
395 quenched with HClO₄ (final 2% v/v), centrifuged and stored at 4°C until analysed.

396 To determine the optimal temperature for the OMT activity, the reactions were incubated in a
397 temperature range of 30–60°C. All subsequent reactions were incubated at 37°C. To investigate metal
398 dependence of the OMTs, different cations (Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺) or EDTA were added
399 to the reaction at a concentration of 2 mM alongside a no additive ("none") control. To study the pH and
400 buffer effects, the reactions were incubated with a 5-fold excess of SAM and 50 mM of the respective
401 buffer (NaPi pH 6; HEPES pH 7; Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 8, 8.5; Glyc-NaOH pH 9, 10, 11). 20 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5)
402 was used for subsequent analyses. For solvent tolerance studies, 0–20% (v/v) of DMSO, methanol or
403 acetonitrile was added to the reaction mix right before the addition of the enzyme. For substrate scope
404 studies, the reactions were incubated for 16 h at 37°C with the addition of 10-20% (v/v) DMSO.

405 Steady-state kinetics

406 Kinetic analyses were performed using 200 nM StrAOMT or 500 nM DesAOMT and 10 to 1000 µM
407 substrate in a reaction mix consisting of 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 20 mM MgCl₂ and 1 mM SAM at 37°C. For
408 the estimation of the initial velocity using linear regression, the reactions were quenched after 5, 10 and
409 15 min with HClO₄ (final 2% v/v), centrifuged and stored at 4°C before HPLC analysis. The peak areas were
410 integrated and converted to concentrations in µM based on calibration curves with the authentic
411 standards. The apparent initial velocities of all experiments performed in triplicate were plotted against
412 substrate concentrations using GraphPad Prism 8 and the apparent K_m and k_{cat} constants were determined
413 by non-linear regression with the Michaelis-Menten equation. A full report of the regression statistics is
414 given in Table S1.

415 Analysis and quantification of OMT reaction products

416 The supernatants of the quenched OMT reactions were analysed by reversed-phase HPLC (instrument:
417 Shimadzu LC-10AT; autosampler: HiP sampler G1367A, T = 4°C, 10 µL injection; flow rate: 1 mL/min;
418 column: Agilent Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C18 80Å, 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 µm, T = 30°C; detector: SPD-20A photodiode
419 array detector (PDA), λ = 275 nm (SAM/SAH; alizarin, DHICA, carnosic acid, pinocembrin, 2-
420 hydroxyestradiol and their methylated products) and λ = 310 nm (all other substrates and their
421 methylated products); solvents A: water with 0.1% TFA, solvent B: ACN with 0.1% TFA; gradient: 10–28%
422 B over 12.5 min; 28–100% B over 9.5 min; 100–10% B over 2 min; 10% B for 3 min.). For analysing the
423 samples of the steady-state kinetics, a shorter program was used: 10–13% B over 2.5 min; 13–25% B over
424 1.5 min; 25–35% B over 2 min; 35–65% B over 2 min; 65–100% B over 1 min; 100–10% B over 3 min; 10%
425 B for 3 min. Product peaks were identified by comparing the retention times to authentic standards
426 (where available). The peak areas were integrated and converted to concentrations in µM based on
427 calibration curves with the authentic standards (where available). Regioisomeric excess (RE) of the
428 reaction was calculated using the formula: $(RE = (c[\text{meta}] - c[\text{para}]) / (c[\text{meta}] + c[\text{para}]) * 100)$.

429 The identity of reaction products was furthermore confirmed by HPLC-coupled mass spectrometry (LCMS)
430 with a Waters Acquity Arc UHPLC-MS equipped with a 2998 PDA, and a QDa single quadrupole mass
431 detector. The samples were separated over an XBridge BEH C18 3.5 µm 2.1 x 50 mm column with a
432 concentration gradient (solvent A: water + 0.1% formic acid, and solvent B: acetonitrile + 0.1% formic acid)
433 at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min (2 µL injections). The following gradient was used: 5% B for 2 min, 5–90% B
434 over 3 min; 90% B for 2 min; 5% B for 3 min.

435 Protein crystallization

436 The sitting-drop vapor diffusion method was applied for crystallization of DesAOMT and StrAOMT at 18°C.
437 Sparse-matrix screening was carried out using the commercial kits JCSG plus, PACT premier, Morpheus,
438 PGA and the MIDAS plus screen (Molecular Dimensions Ltd., UK). Reservoir solution and freshly prepared
439 protein were mixed at a ratio of 1:1 µL. DesAOMT was used at a concentration of 8 mg/ml in 10 mM HEPES
440 pH 7.0, 20 mM NaCl, 0.2 mM MgCl₂, and 5 mM BME. After 5–6 days, a tetragonal bipyramid-shaped crystal
441 appeared in the well containing reservoir solution of 0.1 M MES/Imidazole pH 6.5, 0.03 M MgCl₂, 0.03 M
442 CaCl₂, 20% (v/v) glycerol and 10% (w/v) PEG4000. StrAOMT was concentrated to 13 mg/ml in 10 mM
443 HEPES pH 7, 200 mM NaCl, 0.2 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM DTT and 5% v/v glycerol. Monoclinic crystals of StrAOMT
444 were obtained in a drop containing reservoir solution of 0.1 M MIB (Malonic acid, Imidazole, Boric acid)
445 pH 6.0 and 25% (w/v) PEG1500.

446 For co-crystallization of StrAOMT with SAH, the protein was incubated with 2.67 mM SAM (from a 32 mM
447 stock containing 5 mM H₂SO₄ and 10% (v/v) EtOH) and 2.5 mM caffeic acid (from a 1 M DMSO stock) for
448 half an hour at room temperature prior to crystallization. Reservoir solution for the StrAOMT-SAH complex
449 contained 0.2 M ammonium formate, 10% (w/v) polyvinylpyrrolidone, and 20% (w/v) PEG 4000. Crystals
450 were harvested using nylon loops 3–4 days before the diffraction experiments. The crystals were briefly
451 immersed in cryoprotectants made from reservoir solutions supplemented with glycerol (20–30% (v/v))
452 and flash-cooled in liquid nitrogen.

453 Diffraction data collection, structure determination and refinement

454 Diffraction data were collected at beamline P11 at the PETRA III (DESY, Hamburg, Germany) at 100 K.
455 Auto-processing of diffraction data was carried out with XDSAPP^[33]. Aimless in the CCP4 suite^[34] was used
456 for further truncation of the data and analysis of the merging statistics.

457 The crystal structures were solved through molecular replacement using the MOLREP program^[35]. The
458 apo StrAOMT model was solved using a search model of the monomer of O-methyltransferase from
459 *Bacillus cereus* (PDB entry: 3DUW). Subsequently, the refined model of the apo-StrAOMT monomer
460 served as a search model for the holo-structure of StrAOMT using the DIMPLE pipeline^[36]. Finally, the
461 AlphaFold model (Q1JXV1) was used to solve the DesAOMT structure. All structures were subjected to
462 iterative cycles of refinement and model building using REFMAC5^[37] and Coot^[38]. Automatically
463 determined TLS parameters were used in REFMAC5 for DesAOMT on account of the significant anisotropy
464 detected.

465 PDB deposition

466 All three structures were deposited in the PDB under accession codes 8C9V (DesAOMT), 8C9T (apo-
467 StrAOMT) and 8C9S (holo-StrAOMT).

468 Bioinformatic analyses

469 Multiple sequence alignments were performed with mafft v7.505^[39] (parameters: --maxiterate 1000 –
470 genafpair). Gene neighbourhoods of DesAOMT and StrAOMT and their sequence homologs were
471 visualized with the EFI-GNT webtool^[22] using the Single Sequence Blast option and a neighbourhood
472 window size of 20 genes.

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477 Author contributions

478 NS and KH conceived the study; NS and SD expressed and purified the proteins and performed biochemical
479 characterization; NS and KH analysed biochemical data; LZ and RO performed crystallization and
480 diffraction experiments; LZ, RO and MG determined and refined the crystal structures; NS and KH wrote
481 the manuscript with contributions from LZ, RO and MG; all authors have read and approved the final
482 version of the manuscript.

483 Conflict of interest

484 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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489 References

- 490 [1] K. M. Henry, C. A. Townsend, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2005**, *127*, 3724–3733.
- 491 [2] A. W. Struck, M. L. Thompson, L. S. Wong, J. Micklefield, *ChemBioChem* **2012**, *13*, 2642–2655.
- 492 [3] K. A. Scott, P. B. Cox, J. T. Njardarson, *J. Med. Chem.* **2022**, *65*, 7044–7072.
- 493 [4] D. A. Learmonth, L. E. Kiss, P. Soares-da-Silva, *Int. Rev. Neurobiol.* **2010**, *95*, 119–162.
- 494 [5] D. K. Liscombe, G. V. Louie, J. P. Noel, *Nat. Prod. Rep.* **2012**, *29*, 1238–1250.
- 495 [6] J. T. Nelson, J. Lee, J. W. Sims, E. W. Schmidt, *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **2007**, *73*, 3575–3580.
- 496 [7] W. Li, S. Chou, A. Khullar, B. Gerratana, *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **2009**, *75*, 2958–2963.
- 497 [8] J. Janata, Z. Kamenik, R. Gazak, S. Kadlcik, L. Najmanova, *Nat. Prod. Rep.* **2018**, *35*, 257–289.
- 498 [9] F. Xu, D. Kong, X. He, Z. Zhang, M. Han, X. Xie, P. Wang, H. Cheng, M. Tao, L. Zhang, Z. Deng, S. Lin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 1739–1748.
- 500 [10] Y.-D. Yoon, Y.-H. Park, Y.-S. Yi, Y.-S. Lee, G.-H. Jo, J.-C. Park, J.-H. Ahn, Y.-H. Lim, *J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*
- 501 **2010**, *20*, 1359–1366.
- 502 [11] S. Lee, J. Kang, J. Kim, *Sci. Rep. 2019 91* **2019**, *9*, 1–12.
- 503 [12] Y. Su, H.-P. Li, M. Zhang, X.-W. Ding, J.-H. Xu, Q. Chen, G.-W. Zheng, Y. Su, H. P. Li, M. Zhang, X. W.
- 504 Ding, J. H. Xu, Q. Cheng, G. W. Zheng, *ChemCatChem* **2022**, DOI 10.1002/CCTC.202200844.
- 505 [13] J. H. Cho, Y. Park, J. H. Ahn, Y. Lim, S. Rhee, *J. Mol. Biol.* **2008**, *382*, 987–997.
- 506 [14] K. Haslinger, T. Hackl, K. L. J. Prather, *Cell Chem. Biol.* **2021**, *28*, 876-886.e4.
- 507 [15] J. L. Rodrigues, D. Gomes, L. R. Rodrigues, *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **2020**, *8*, 59.
- 508 [16] A. R. Brochado, C. Matos, B. L. Møller, J. Hansen, U. H. Mortensen, K. R. Patil, *Microb. Cell Factories*
- 509 **2010**, *9*, 1–15.
- 510 [17] A. M. Kunjapur, K. L. J. Prather, *ACS Synth. Biol.* **2019**, *8*, 1958–1967.
- 511 [18] A. M. Kunjapur, J. C. Hyun, K. L. J. Prather, *Microb. Cell Factories* **2016**, *15*, 61.
- 512 [19] M. Dippe, M. D. Davari, B. Weigel, R. Heinke, T. Vogt, L. A. Wessjohann, *ChemCatChem* **2022**, *14*,
- 513 e202200511.
- 514 [20] X. Wang, C. Wang, L. Duan, L. Zhang, H. Liu, Y. M. Xu, Q. Liu, T. Mao, W. Zhang, M. Chen, M. Lin, A. A.
- 515 L. Gunatilaka, Y. Xu, I. Molnár, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 4355–4364.
- 516 [21] W. Brandt, K. Manke, T. Vogt, *Phytochemistry* **2015**, *113*, 130–139.
- 517 [22] R. Zallot, N. Oberg, J. A. Gerlt, *Biochemistry* **2019**, *58*, 4169–4182.
- 518 [23] J. Siegrist, J. Netzer, S. Mordhorst, L. Karst, S. Gerhardt, O. Einsle, M. Richter, J. N. Andexer, *FEBS Lett.*
- 519 **2017**, *591*, 312–321.
- 520 [24] K. Somailetha Chandran, J. Humphries, J. Q. D. Goodger, I. E. Woodrow, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2022**, *23*, 3190.
- 521 [25] S. Singh, N. S. Nandurkar, J. S. Thorson, S. Singh, N. S. Nandurkar, J. S. Thorson, *ChemBioChem* **2014**,
- 522 *15*, 1418–1421.
- 523 [26] L. Holm, *Nucleic Acids Res.* **2022**, *50*, W210–W215.
- 524 [27] J. G. Kopycki, M. T. Stubbs, W. Brandt, M. Hagemann, A. Porzel, J. Schmidt, W. Schliemann, M. H. Zenk,
- 525 T. Vogt, *J. Biol. Chem.* **2008**, *283*, 20888–20896.
- 526 [28] X. Hou, Y. Wang, Z. Zhou, S. Bao, Y. Lin, W. Gong, *J. Struct. Biol.* **2007**, *159*, 523–528.
- 527 [29] B. J. C. Law, M. R. Bennett, M. L. Thompson, C. Levy, S. A. Shepherd, D. Leys, J. Micklefield, *Angew.*
- 528 *Chem. - Int. Ed.* **2016**, *55*, 2683–2687.
- 529 [30] S. H. Lee, B. Kim, K. J. Kim, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **2021**, *69*, 2531–2538.
- 530 [31] J. G. Kopycki, D. Rauh, A. A. Chumanevich, P. Neumann, T. Vogt, M. T. Stubbs, *J. Mol. Biol.* **2008**, *378*,
- 531 154–164.
- 532 [32] X. He, Z. Wei, J. Wang, J. Kou, W. Liu, Y. Fu, Z. Yang, *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 28370.

- 533 [33] M. Krug, M. S. Weiss, U. Heinemann, U. Mueller, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* **2012**, *45*, 568–572.
- 534 [34] M. D. Winn, C. C. Ballard, K. D. Cowtan, E. J. Dodson, P. Emsley, P. R. Evans, R. M. Keegan, E. B. Krissinel,
535 A. G. W. Leslie, A. McCoy, S. J. McNicholas, G. N. Murshudov, N. S. Pannu, E. A. Potterton, H. R. Powell,
536 R. J. Read, A. Vagin, K. S. Wilson, *Acta Crystallogr. D Biol. Crystallogr.* **2011**, *67*, 235–242.
- 537 [35] A. Vagin, A. Teplyakov, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* **1997**, *30*, 1022–1025.
- 538 [36] M. Wojdyr, R. Keegan, G. Winter, A. Ashton, *Acta Crystallogr. A* **2013**, *69*, 299–299.
- 539 [37] G. N. Murshudov, P. Skubák, A. A. Lebedev, N. S. Pannu, R. A. Steiner, R. A. Nicholls, M. D. Winn, F.
540 Long, A. A. Vagin, *Acta Crystallogr. D Biol. Crystallogr.* **2011**, *67*, 355–367.
- 541 [38] P. Emsley, K. Cowtan, *Acta Crystallogr. D Biol. Crystallogr.* **2004**, *60*, 2126–2132.
- 542 [39] K. Katoh, D. M. Standley, *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **2013**, *30*, 772–780.
- 543